

THE EFFECT OF SQUEEZE CASTING AND HOT EXTRUSION PROCESS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SIC_p/AL COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The silicon carbide particulate reinforced metal matrix composites were fabricated by melt-stirring method. The volume fractions of reinforcements were 5vol% to 20vol% and the mean size 13 to 22. Then MMC billets were extruded at 500 under the constant extrusion velocity of 2mm/min. Extrusion force, particle rearrangement, microstructure and mechanical properties of both primary billets and extruded bars have been investigated. The properties that were most useful in extruded composite products were the increased modulus of elasticity and strength. Through extrusion process, the particles could be more homogeneously distributed along the extrusion direction. Experimental values of Young's modulus and 0.2% offset yield strength for extruded composites were compared with theoretical values calculated by the Eshelby model.

KEYWORD: metal matrix composites, melt-stirring method, squeeze casting, homogeneous distribution, hot extrusion, optimal die

INTRODUCTION

In fabrication process of light parts, considerable attention has been given to the fabrication and property characterization of metal matrix composites. These composite systems have exhibited improvements in not only mechanical properties at room and elevated temperatures but also wear behavior. And high directional properties can be obtained by the secondary processing, such as extrusion, rolling, and forging etc.[1-4] Among the fabrication methods the mechanical agitation method which is to stir the liquid metal with solid ceramic particles have the problems as follows ; the uniform distribution of the reinforcements is disturbed due to the low wettability and the density difference between the molten metal and the reinforcements. Mechanical properties of extruded composites depend on many factors, e.g. degassing condition before extrusion and the extrusion conditions. If these parameters are chosen correctly, considerable improvements in tensile strength compared with the unreinforced alloy can be achieved. In this study, the particulate reinforced composites were manufactured with the distribution method improved on the convenient experimental equipment[5]. After tensile testing of primary specimens, fracture surfaces were examined in the SEM and microhardness measurements were carried out on polished specimens. To improve the mechanical properties, the primary billets were hot extruded with curved die. Tensile properties of the primary and secondary specimens were examined with the calculated results by Eshelby's theory[6].

EXPERIMENTAL

Al6061 alloy (Al-Si-Mg) was employed in this study [7]. The green silicon carbide particles (Norton 39 Crystolon grain) used in the experiments were supplied by Norton Company [8]. Manufacturing methods of primary billets were as follows. When the temperature of molten metal reached 670, particle addition was started. The impeller speed was controlled as 750 rpm and the preheating temperature of particles was 650. The temperature of the mold was 200. Applied pressure was 100 MPa. The speed of injection plunger was 16 mm/sec and the pressure time was 30 sec. The fabricated billets were of 44 mm diameter and of 70~80 mm height [4].

The extrusion experiment was carried out with the curved die of constant strain rate. Die profile as a function of die length Z was described by [9]

$$R(Z) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\pi} \frac{F_0}{(\lambda - 1)Z/L + 1}} \quad (1)$$

- R : die profile
 F_0 : initial cross section area in billet (mm^2)
 λ : extrusion ratio (D_1^2/D_2^2)
 Z : extrusion direction
 L : die length (mm)

Fig.1: Curved shape die used for hot extrusion.

Table1. Die dimensions used for hot extrusion

$D_0(\text{mm})$	$D_1(\text{mm})$	$D_2(\text{mm})$	L	h	H	λ
84	35	12	15	4	25	8.51

Fig.1 shows the curved shape die used for hot extrusion. The equipments for hot extrusion were composed of 25 ton universal testing machine, heating furnace, extrusion punch, upper/lower container, extrusion die and dummy block [9]. Table 1 shows die dimensions and extrusion ratio (λ) used for hot extrusion. The primary billets manufactured by melt stirring and squeeze casting were fabricated for extrusion billets by machine. The billets were fabricated to diameters of 35 mm and lengths of 60 mm. The billets, extrusion die and dummy block were put in upper container and were kept constant at the experimental temperature by furnace. The experimental temperature was set to 500. It was observed through a preliminary

experiments that the surface appearance of MMCs extruded by the conventional extrusion method was smooth at the ram speed 2mm/sec.

Fig.2(a)-(d): Effects of the volume fraction of reinforcement on mechanical properties of SiC_p(13)/Al6061.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The specimens were heat-treated by a T6 thermal treatment and tested, at room temperature, on an MTS at a cross head velocity of 1/min.

Fig.2(a)(d) shows the effects of the volume fraction of reinforcement on mechanical properties of SiC_p(13)/Al6061. Fig.2(a) shows the tensile strength according to the variation of volume fraction of reinforcements. Tensile strength of the unreinforced Al6061 was rather higher than that of the reinforced materials. In SiC_p(13)/Al6061 composites manufactured by the melt-stirring and squeeze casting, when the volume fraction of reinforcements was above 5vol%, ultimate strength could be improved.

Fig.2(b) shows the variation of elastic modulus with the volume fraction of reinforcement. The elastic modulus was proportional to the volume fraction of reinforcement. Fig.2(c) shows the relationship between the elongation and the volume fraction. Elongations were decreased

with increasing volume fraction. Hardness tests were performed on a Rockwell Hardness Machine (B scale). In Fig.2(d), the increase of hardness was proportional to volume fraction.

Fig.3(a)-(d): Effects of reinforcement content on mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_p(22)/\text{Al6061}$.

Fig.3(a)(d) shows the effects of the volume fraction of reinforcement on mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_p(22)/\text{Al6061}$.

In Fig.4(a)(c), SEM examinations were conducted on the tensile fracture surfaces. Some specimens failed during tensile testing, achieving lower than ultimate strength and elongation of the wrought Al6061. In all of these cases macroscopic features were observed on the fracture surfaces that could be correlated to the occurrence in the microstructure of large defects from the fabrication and processing of the material. In Fig.4(a) and Fig.4(b) for 5vol% and 10vol%, respectively, the large dimples were associated with SiC particulates. The smaller dimples were not associated with ductile fibrous failure of the aluminum matrix. This is consistent with the low ductility of these materials. In Fig.4(c) fracture surfaces of composite with the reinforcement of 15vol% were similar. Fracture surfaces consisted of cracked SiC particulates embedded in larger dimples and surrounded by finely dimpled aluminum matrix. As the interface bonding force between the matrix and the reinforcements was stronger, the ductile fracture regions Fig.4(c) were larger than those of Fig.4(a) and Fig.4(b). The improvement of strengthening effectiveness could be expected above 10vol% in $\text{SiC}_p(22)/\text{Al6061}$ composites manufactured by only melt-stirring and squeeze casting process.

SiC_p/Al6061 composites fabricated by the melt-stirring and squeeze casting couldn't exhibit improved mechanical properties as compared to the unreinforced Al6061.

Fig.5(a)(d) shows mechanical properties of 13 SiC_p /Al6061 extruded as function of volume fraction. In Fig.5(a), ultimate strengths for the volume fraction of 5, 10, 15 and 20vol% were 335, 339, 351 and 361MPa, respectively. After hot extrusion process, the ultimate strength was increased higher, about 25% to 35%, than that of the specimens fabricated by only melt-stirring and squeeze casting. From this results, it was improved linearly with increasing the volume fraction of the reinforcements.

Fig.4: SEM fractograph of Al6061/SiC_p tensile specimen (average size of SiC_p=22).

Fig.5(a)-(d): Mechanical properties of $\text{SiC}_p(13)/\text{Al6061}$ extruded as function of volume fraction.

Elastic modulus was proportioned to the increase of volume fraction in Fig.5(b). Elongation for the volume fraction 5, 10, 15 and 20vol% were 5.02, 3.08, 3.05 and 2.48%, respectively, in Fig.5(c). With the increase of the volume fraction, the stiffness was increased, however, the elongation was decreased. Fig.5(d) shows Rockwell hardness. Hardness for the volume fraction 5, 10, 15 and 20vol% were 55, 58.4, 67 and 70.7HR, respectively. Elastic modulus and hardness for the MMC specimens were improved linearly with increasing the volume fraction of the particles regardless of hot extrusion. Through extrusion process, however, the particles could be more homogeneously distributed along the extrusion direction.

Fig.6(a)(c) shows the microstructure for composites. The mean size of SiC_p is 13 and the volume fraction of SiC_p is 10vol%. The particulate reinforcements within the composite billet were conglomerated in the entry of extrusion container and were aligned in the middle of the container. The distribution state of the particulate reinforcements was improved in the exit of it[11].

Fig.6: Microstructure of particle arrangement during hot extrusion process with 13size, $V_f=10\text{vol}\%$ (a)Die entry (b)Die middle (c)Die exit (\rightarrow : extrusion direction).

Fig.7: Eshelby's cutting and welding model.

THEORETICAL MODEL AND RESULTS

Eshelby's cutting and welding model is shown in Fig.7. The region of the reinforcement is cut from the unstressed elastically homogeneous material and the shape change is imagined to undergo a size change as a uniform ellipsoid. Then the strain is defined as the transformation strain ϵ^T . Surface tractions to make $\epsilon=0$ are applied in order to return to its initial shape before removal. There is no sliding along the interface between the matrix region and the reinforcement region, and the surface tractions are then removed. When equilibrium is reached, strain is defined as a constrained strain ϵ^C . The stress within the reinforcement can be calculated in terms of the strain ($\epsilon^C - \epsilon^T$) and the stiffness tensor of the material C_M [12].

$$\sigma_I = C_M(\epsilon^C - \epsilon^T) \quad (2)$$

ϵ^C can be obtained from ϵ^T by means of Eshelby ' S_{ij} ' tensor.

Fig.8: Comparison between the extrusion and Eshelby theory (13 SiC_p)

Fig.9: Comparison of 0.2% offset yield strength between the experimental results (22 SiC_p) and the theoretical analysis ($s=1.5$)

$$\epsilon^C = S_{ij} \epsilon^T \quad (3)$$

Mixture rule is used to include the volume fraction f of all the inclusions.

$$(1-f) \langle \sigma \rangle_M + f \langle \sigma \rangle_I = 0 \rightarrow \langle \sigma \rangle_M = -\frac{f}{1-f} \langle \sigma \rangle_I \quad (4)$$

The mean stresses are given as follows ;

$$\langle \sigma \rangle_M = -f C_M (S_{ij} - I) \epsilon^T, \quad \langle \sigma \rangle_I = (1-f) C_M (S_{ij} - I) \epsilon^T \quad (5)$$

Leading to the equation for the composite stiffness tensor C_C

$$C_C = [C_M^{-1} - f \{ (C_M - C_I) [S - f(S - I)] - C_M \}^{-1} \times (C_M - C_I) C_M^{-1} \Gamma^{-1} \quad (6)$$

The relation between the stress σ^A and the strain ε^A by the applied load can be written with the composite stiffness tensor.

$$\sigma^A = C_c (\varepsilon^A + \bar{\varepsilon}^A) \rightarrow \varepsilon_3^A + \bar{\varepsilon}_3^A = C_{3c}^{-1} \sigma^A = \frac{\sigma^A}{E_{3c}} \quad (7)$$

(E_{3c} : axial Young's modulus)

Fig.8 represents the comparison between experimental datas and theoretical analyses of the Eshelby model for SiC_p(13)/Al6061 composites. The mean values of experimental datas were within the limits of aspect ratios 1.1 to 2.0. It was difficult to obtain the uniform distribution of reinforcements through the conventional manufacturing, resulting in particle clustering and low work of adhesion. Experimental datas can be predicted with Eshelby approaches in the elastic region.

Tresca yield criterion is written as

$$\sigma_{YM} = \bar{\sigma}_{3M} - \bar{\sigma}_{1M} (= \Delta\sigma) \quad (8)$$

Flow occurs at an applied stress σ^A equal to

$$\sigma^A = \sigma_{YM} - (\langle \sigma_3 \rangle_M^A - \langle \sigma_1 \rangle_M^A) \quad (9)$$

The deviatric stress $\Delta\sigma$ to occur the yield stress in the matrix region may be written as

$$\Delta\sigma = (\bar{\sigma}_{3M} - \bar{\sigma}_{1M}) = \sigma^A + (\langle \sigma_3 \rangle_M^A - \langle \sigma_1 \rangle_M^A) \quad (10)$$

In Fig.9, when the volume fractions of reinforcements were 5vol%, 10vol%, 15vol% and 20vol%, after extrusion, 0.2% offset yield stresses for SiC_p(22)/Al6061 composites were 319MPa, 321MPa, 333MPa and 340MPa, respectively. The theoretical values were about - 1.5%, 2.4%, 3.3%, 5.7% higher than the experimental values, resulting from various reinforcement size high particle aspect ratio and local stress concentration in the vicinity of the reinforcements. Due to a factor of the inner defects this phenomenon appear in the initial deformation of the composites. It is very difficult to predict exactly mechanical properties of particulate reinforced metal matrix composites.

CONCLUSIONS

Mechanical properties of primary billets manufactured by melt-stirring and squeeze casting method were compared with both the strengths of extrusion specimen and the predicted values of Eshelby model for SiC_p/Al6061 composites, respectively. The following results were obtained by theoretical and experimental datas.

- (1) SiC_p/Al6061 composites fabricated by the melt-stirring and squeeze casting couldn't exhibit improved mechanical properties as compared to the unreinforced Al6061.
- (2) After hot extrusion process, the ultimate strength was increased about 25% to 35%, which is higher than that of the specimens fabricated by only melt-stirring and squeeze

- casting. From this results, it was improved linearly with increasing the volume fraction of the reinforcements.
- (3) Elastic modulus and hardness for the MMC specimens were improved linearly with increasing the volume fraction of the particles regardless of hot extrusion. Through extrusion process, however, the particles could be more homogeneously distributed along the extrusion direction.
 - (4) The experimental results obtained through an extrusion process of SiC_p/Al6061 composite were in a good agreement with the theoretical datas.

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